

THE RELATIONSHIP OF ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE TO PUPILS BEHAVIOR OF SELECTED ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS OF JOLO DISTRICT III

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the relationship of organizational climate to pupils' behavior of selected of selected elementary schools of Jolo District III. Specifically to: 1) Determine the organizational climate of selected Schools of Jolo District III. 2) Identify the behavior of the pupils. Teachers comprised favorable organizational climate in Jolo District III in terms of esprit, intimacy. However the existence of hindrance and disengagement seemed insignificant Teachers were given free-time to strengthen their closeness and shared their experiences. On the same view, the principal dimensions were also favorable in terms of consideration, thrust, and production emphasis. Only in the aspect of aloofness seemed unfavorable. The performance of the principal had correspondent reactions and responses from the teachers primarily conformed to the existing theory on organizational climate. Besides, the pupils comprising the academic competitiveness, concern for individual pupils' school spirit and emphasis on social life behavior were favorable In other words pupils have commended the prevailing conditions in the school system. From the data gathered the following conclusions were derived: 1. that the organizational climates under teachers dimension is characterized by teachers quarrel and criticize each other is rejected. 2. That the pupils like their teachers are accepted. 3. That there exists a relationship between school climate and pupils behavior is accepted. Any study had always the loopholes to be strengthened. With these the following propositions are suggested: 1. The principal shall come up with activities and programs that the several memberships of the faculty members can socialize themselves to strengthen cohesiveness. 2. They shall also come up with strategic programs that there may create intimacy between the pupils and the principal. 3. Minority group specially expressing their sentiments, needs and demands shall be addressed to prevent the occurring of factionalism or strife among themselves. 4. Follow-up study especially on

correlating the pupils' behavior and the managerial performance shall be conducted. 5. Additional variables shall be added to the present study for further explorations.

Keywords: *Organizational Climate, Pupils Behavior, Descriptive Research, Jolo District*

INTRODUCTION

The atmosphere, tone or ambience of an organization permeates the entire organization. Like the weather, it is important to be considered in the lives of the individuals and so with the climate of organization in which there exists a web of interaction among individuals. Thus, school climate and student behavior must be considered as (Halpin and Croft) conceived of social climate of school as a blend of two dimensions: the principal's leadership and interaction.

Climate of an institution has been found to relate to some aspects of students' behavior, in spite of individual differences in the perception of school climate. School climate as perceived by students and teachers can be a significant predictor of student achievement. After controlling for student scholastic ability and community socioeconomic status, they found that climate retained significant predictive power, suggesting that school climate is related to student achievement.

This component of school climate pertains to the leaders, style of interacting with the teachers. The way the principal behaves, as has been noted, influences the ways in which the teachers interact with each other and thus has considerable impact on the general atmosphere of the school, influences the ways in which teachers interact with each other and thus has considerable impact on the general atmosphere of the school, Halpin (1966).

Psychological studies of human behaviors, which began in the late 19th and early 20th centuries in Europe and later in America, revealed a new paradigm of science known as Behaviorism through the establishment of experimental laboratories (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2008). Behaviorism has explored behaviors that can always be observed and quantitatively measured in controlled laboratory conditions. While the behaviorist approach focuses on the behaviors that are observable in individuals, it has ignored possible internal factors such as motivation and mental mechanisms such as thinking. This approach has had implications for organizational structures of educational programs, students, teachers, teaching methods and educational institutions. Accordingly, educational objectives should be defined as behavior-oriented. In the 1900s, the existence of subliminal instincts in human behavior was discussed and it was stated that the motives of people are some of the reasons for behaviors. These theories later became the basis for scales developed for personality profiles (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2008; Owens & Valesky, 2011; Woolfolk, 2014). The cognitive and social psychologies that emerged in the 1960s were considered as the primary components of the scientific foundations of education and had great impact on the concepts of learning and teaching. However, when describing an individual's behavior, one must focus on the interaction

between personal characteristics and the social characteristics of the group or organization in which that behavior occurs. When describing organizational behavior, it is necessary to consider the influence of the social circle in which the organization is located (Glisson & James, 2002; Owens & Valesky, 2011; Roeser, Urdan & Stephens, 2009).

The key administrative behavior patterns, thrust- the energy and drive the principal exhibits as a role model for teachers. Principals who are in evidence in their buildings, observing what transpires, offering helpful suggestions, and mentioning new techniques at appropriate times, can help teachers focus on their tasks and sharpen their professional skills, Genuine consideration for teachers could help in resolving problems that might interfere with teaching, it might also help teachers feel secure enough to share their teaching problems and seek advice honestly rather than withholding such information for fear of reprisals Sharing of information in the form of ideas, suggestions advice and problems can help individuals learn how to resolve their own teaching problems and facilitate the dissemination of the best fosters or impede communication. Then, the climate of the school is related to the quality of instruction students receive, Silver (1983).

The climate of an institution has been found to relate to some aspects of students behavior. Despite of individual differences in the perception of school climate Schools do seem to have distinctive climates that relate to students achievement Because of the potential importance of the general tone of a school with respect to student outcomes further research of school climate should be energetically pursued. Hence, the researcher chosen the said study, since there was clearly demonstrated relationship between school climate and students behavior considering academic competitiveness, school spirit concern for individual pupils, emphasis on social life.

Bloom (2010) identified ten components of organizational climate in the light of the studies that she conducted for many years in early childhood centers. These components are collegiality, professional development, director support, clarity, reward system, decision-making, goal consensus, task orientation, physical environment and innovation.

The focus of this undertaking is to determine the relationship of the organizational climate and students' behavior among selected elementary schools of Jolo District III

Research Questions

This study drew attention to the following interrelated problems

1. What are the organizational climate of selected schools of Jolo district III?
2. What are the behaviors of the pupils?
3. Do the different climates have relationship to pupils' behavior?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted the causal descriptive because it sought to undergo research on the existing school climate and pupils behavior of Jolo District III. It delved with present phenomenon, then it is descriptive

On the other hand it established relationship of variables on the school climate and student behavior then it was causal

Sampling Procedure

Simple random sampling was used to get the ideal number of the respondents of this study. Besides, stratified random sampling was used so that there is equal distribution of respondents to be selected in every elementary school in Jolo District III would be observed

With this, selection of respondent was done scientifically so us to observe the ethical principles of research. In addition it also preserved the reliability and validity of data gathered. And 50 percent of the total population of the selected elementary schools were used as respondents.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the elementary teachers handling any grade, regardless of their sex, length of service educational attainment and civil status There were (90) teachers considered as respondent with the following numbers respectively Tanjung Elementary Schools twenty nine (29), Bakud Elementary school thirty four (34), Jati Elementary School twenty seven (27). However respondents were classified to two major groups intermediate and primary level.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in three selected schools of Jolo District III which is considered having a densely enrollees, Bakud Elementary School located inside the Philippine Constabulary Compound adjacent to DXSM Radio Station which considered as one of the best schools in town as evident on the quality pupils they are producing has (34) thirty four teachers, Jati Elementary School Located near 477, Asturias, Jolo, Sulu has (27) twenty seven teachers and Tanjung Elementary school Located at Km 2 has (29) twenty nine teachers.

Research Instrument

The data gathering instrument used in this study was the survey questionnaire. The questionnaire checklist is divided into three parts. The first part covers the personal

data of the elementary school teachers. The second part comprises the checklist for organizational climate for both teacher and principal dimension. The last part deals with the pupils' behavior description questionnaire.

The researcher used "often" in the checklist choices and implied "conducive on the descriptive interpretation of the data.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the approval from the District Supervisor of the selected school in Jolo District III prior to the approval from the respective principals. After which, the researcher proceeded immediately to the classroom adviser and the teacher respondent.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Two (2) statistical tools were used in the analysis of the responses of the respondents. Weighted mean was used to describe the climate dimensions and pupils behavior. Mean was computed by using this formula
This formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{X}{n}$$

Where \bar{X} = mean

X = summation of all observations

n = number of total observations

On the other hand, Spearman Rank order correlation coefficient was used to determine the extent of relationship between organizational climate and pupil's behavior

The formula is:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

Where N = the number of pairs

r_s = the rank-order correlation coefficient

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teacher Dimensions

The study revealed that, in esprit, the organizational climate was ranging from very conducive (Very favorable) to conducive (favorable) (Table Ia) This means that the following occur often in these selected schools of Jolo III District 1) The morale of teachers is high 2) Teachers accomplish their work with vigor and enthusiasm 3) Teachers spend

time after school with students who have individual problems 4) Teachers accept easily the faults of their colleagues.

As to the intimacy, the same result was obtained with the first dimension (esprit) (Table 4 la) The following also occur often in these district 1) Teacher's closest friends are other faculty members in this school 2) Teachers talk about their personal life to ether faculty members 3) Teachers have fun socializing together during school time 4) Teachers invite other faculty members to their homes That is, these are favorable in this selected schools

For the hindrance, the following cases often occur in the district 1) Teachers are involved in too many extra-curricular activities 2) Administrative paper work is burdensome in this school 3). Pupils' progress reports (grading sheets, report cards, summative tests, etc) require too much work. That is, organizational climate in terms of hindrance was found not conducive (Table 1a).

In terms of disengagement, the climate was faulty favorable in the following two cases 1). There is a minority group of teachers who always oppose the majority 2) Teachers socialize together in small select group 3). Teachers quarrel and criticize each other 4) Teachers talk about leaving the school, system Such two cases sometimes occur in this district However, there was a favorable climate in the sense that teachers rarely quarrel and criticize each other (table 4 la), which it was found not favorable in that teachers socialize together in small select group.

The data as revealed in this study implied that teacher's dimensions on organizational climate were complex Le a combination of classical and neo-classical principles Classical as exposed by Frederick Taylor gave emphasis on the strictness of work performance Teachers would be given various loads expecting to achieve high organization performance In other words, the teachers focused on work orientation Formal structure, thus, was observed

On the same view, informal organization structure was also observed. This is the focus of neo-classical approach where the teachers' needs, morale and leisure time were allowed Teachers, therefore, were given freedom to form association and establish rapport relationship among others.

In a nutshell, there existed a Hawthorn effect where in a bureaucratic or highly organized structures of school, informal organization was given due-recognition.

Jolo District III, in consequence, could predict stability and good performance considering that disengagement was fairly observed. Moreover, factionalism or professional jealousy, as it was called, was insignificant.

Table 1a. Organizational Climate of Selected Schools in Jolo District III in terms of Teacher Dimension, 2005 - 2006

Organizational Climate	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	
Teacher Dimensions			
a. Esprit (+)	4.10	Often	Conductive
1. The morale of teachers is high.	4.79	Very Often	Very Conductive
2. Teachers accomplish their work with vigor and enthusiasm.	4.14	Often	Conductive
3. Teachers spend time after school with students who have individual problems.	3.73	Often	Conductive
4. Teachers accept easily the faults of their colleagues.	3.73	Often Often	Conductive Conductive
B. Intimacy (+)	4.07	Very Often	Very Conductive
1. Teacher's closest friends are other faculty members in this school.	4.68	Often	Conductive
2. Teachers talk about their personal life to ether faculty members	3.85	Often	Conductive
3. Teachers have fun socializing together during school time	3.69	Often	Conductive
4. Teachers invite other faculty members to their homes.	4.07	Often Often	Not Conductive Not Conductive
C. Hindrance (-)	3.60	Often	Not Conductive
1. Teachers are involved in too many extra-curricular activities.	3.55		
2. Administrative paper work is burdensome in this school.	3.55	Often Sometimes	Not Conductive Fairly Conductive
3. Pupils progress reports (grading sheets, repon cards, summative tests, etc) require too much work.	3.71	Sometimes	Fairly Conductive
D. Disengagement (-)	3.04	Often	Not Conductive
1. There is a minority group of teachers who always oppose the majority.	3.20	Rarely Sometimes	Conductive Fairly Conductive
2. Teachers socialize together in small select group.	3.60		
3. Teachers quarrel and criticize each other.	2.31		
4. Teachers talk about leaving the school; system.	3.03		

Legend Means	Occurrence	For Esprit and Intimacy Climate Status	For Hindrance and Disengagement
1.00 – 1.49 =	Never Occurs	= Not Conductive at all	= Very Conductive
1.50 – 2.49 =	Rarely Occurs	= Not Conductive	= Conductive
2.50 – 3.49 =	Sometimes Occurs	= Fairly Conductive	= Fairly Conductive
3.50 – 4.49 =	Often Occurs	= Conductive	= Not Conductive

4.50 – 5.00 = Very often Occurs = Very Conducive = Not Conducive

Principal Dimension

Findings revealed that the organizational climate of selected schools in Jolo District III was found favorable (Conducive) in terms of principal dimension, especially on the aspects of consideration, thrust, and production emphasis. This was however, not favorable in the aspect of aloofness (Table 1 a) Consideration aspect includes 1) the principal helps teachers solve their personal problems 2) The principal helps staff members settle minor differences. 3) The principal helps stays after school, to help teachers finish their work. 4). the principal tries to get better salaries/incentive for teachers. On the aspect of thrust, these are: 1) The principal sets an example by working hard himself/herself 2) The principal is well-prepared when he speaks at school functions 3) The principal tells teachers of new ideas/thrust in education 4) The principal arrives early in school and stays late when needed. In the production Emphasis, these includes 1) the principal checks the subject matter ability of teachers. 2) The principal schedules the work for the teachers 3) the principal insures that the teachers work to their full capacity. All of those cases were found often in their occurrence. As to aloofness, which is a negative aspect, includes the following 1) The principal runs the faculty meetings like a business conference 2). The rules set by the principal are not questioned by subordinates 3) Faculty meeting are organized according to a tight agenda 4) Principal keeps from teachers' result of a supervisor's/superiors supervisory visits. Each of these cases in the aloofness occur "often" which indicates not favorable.

Table 1b. Organizational Climate of Selected Schools in Jolo District III in terms of Principal Dimensions.

Organizational Climate	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	
Principal Dimensions		Often	Conducive
A. Consideration (+)	4.08	Often	Conducive
1. The principal helps teachers solve their personal problems	4.34	Often	Conducive
2. The principal helps staff members settle minor differences.	3.85	Often	Conducive
3. The principal helps stays after school, to help teachers finish their work.	4.18	Often	Conducive
4. The principal tries to get better salaries/incentive for teachers.	3.96	Often	Conducive
B. Thrust (+)	4.26	Often	Conducive
1. The principal sets an example by working hard himself/herself	4.39	Often	Conducive
2. The principal is well-prepared when he speaks at school functions	4.19	Often	Conducive
3. The principal tells teachers of new ideas/thrust in education	4.27	Often	Conducive
4. The principal arrives early in school and stays late when needed	4.21	Often	Conducive

C. Production Emphasis (+)	4.14	Often	Conductive
1. The principal checks the subject matter ability of teachers	4.27	Often	Conductive
2. The principal schedules the work for the teachers	3.97	Often Often	Not Conductive Not Conductive
3. The principal insures that the teachers work to their full capacity	4.18	Often	Not Conductive
D. Aloofnes (-)	3.74	Often	Not Conductive
1. The principal runs the faculty meetings like a business conference	4.18	Often	Not Conductive
2. The rules set by the principal are not questioned by subordinates	3.52		
3. Faculty meeting are organized according to a tight agenda	3.57		
4. Principal keeps from teachers' result of a supervisor's/superiors supervisory visits.	3.71		

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.49 = Never Occurs
- 1.50 – 2.49 = Rarely Occurs
- 2.50 – 3.49 = Sometimes Occurs
- 3.50 – 4.49 = Often Occurs
- 4.50 – 5.00 = Very often Occurs

The school head concerned for people in such a way that he understood and supported his staff and the teachers. Similarly he emphasized also the concern for production where tasks were delegated and achieving the organizational goals the vision and mission of school system.

Davis and Newstrom in their book "Human Behavior in organization" expressed about supportive leadership where the executive is trying to understand the needs of their subordinates, provide leadership advancement and encourage his people for greater achievement. Similarly, koontz and Wehrich (1997) in "Essentials of Management called it Path-Goal Theory of leadership where people and production were harmonized in realizing the goals of the school. The goals are always the parameter and the direction of the school.

Chester Barnard in his book "The functions of Executive" as cited in the "Administrative Thinkers" by Prasad and Prasad (1997) pointed out that there is a need to recognize the informal organization like click and group work within the context of formal structure.

With the existence of aloofness which is not favorable to the organizational structure of the school, Jolo District III, therefore, was on its way to growth and

development. The school environment as demonstrated by the principal could be counted as necessary factor for the District III to develop within the content of its mandate.

Behavior of Pupils in Selected Schools of Jolo District III

Academic Competitiveness

Findings revealed that the behavior of pupils in selected schools in Jolo district III in terms of **academic competitiveness** was favorable with one aspect of very favorable which is pupils participate daily classroom activities (Table 2a) That is, the following activities on the part of the pupils occur "often" 1) Pupils attend their classes. 2) Pupils participate daily classroom activities 3) Pupils take time to study their lessons. 4) Pupils accomplish their homework or assignment. 5) Pupils express themselves correctly when speaking or writing. 6) Pupils participate in academic competitions like quiz bee, oratorical contests and other similar activities. 7) Pupils go to the library to read. 8) Pupils discuss current events or happenings on the local, national and international levels with other pupils and other people in school. 9) Pupils ask their teachers questions about their lessons.

Table 2a. Behavior of Pupils in Selected Schools of Jolo District III in terms of Academic Competitiveness.

Pupils Behavior	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Academic Competitiveness	4.23	Often
1. Pupils attend their classes.	4.69	Favorable
2. Pupils participate daily classroom activities	4.33	Very Often
3. Pupils take time to study their lessons.	4.18	Favorable
4. Pupils accomplish their homework or assignment.	4.16	Often Favorable
5. Pupils express themselves correctly when speaking or writing.	4.07	Often Favorable
6. Pupils participate in academic competitions like quiz bee, oratorical contests and other similar activities.	4.26	Often Favorable
7. Pupils go to the library to read.	3.89	Often
8. Pupils discuss current events or happenings on the local, national and international levels with other pupils and other people in school	4.21	Favorable
9. Pupils ask their teachers questions about their lessons.	4.34	Often Favorable

Besides, attendance of the pupils in the classroom session really mattered. And, it is one of the contributing factors that develop children in the academic performance This is quite true to schools like ours where teachers are the usual source of knowledge, skills and values.

Concern for Individual Pupils

Concern for individual pupils as one aspect of pupils' behavior was found favorable in that the following cases occurred "often" in the district. 1) Pupils are friendly to their classmates/schoolmates. 2) Pupils listen to the problems of their classmates/schoolmates. 3). Pupils help their academically weak classmates / schoolmates with their lessons or homework/ assignments. 4) Pupils respect the religious beliefs and opinions of their classmates/schoolmates. 5) Pupils easily accept the mistakes of their classmates/schoolmates. 6) Pupils visit their sick classmates/ schoolmates. 7) Pupils offer their money to help their classmates/schoolmates who are in need.

Table 2b

Pupils Behavior	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Concern for Individual Pupils	4.19	Often
1. Pupils are friendly to their classmates/schoolmates.	4.56	Favorable
2. Pupils listen to the problems of their classmates/schoolmates.	4.18	Often Favorable
3. Pupils help their academically weak classmates / schoolmates with their lessons or homework/ assignments.	4.15	Often Favorable
4. Pupils respect the religious beliefs and opinions of their classmates/schoolmates.	4.25	Often Favorable
5. Pupils easily accept the mistakes of their classmates/schoolmates.	4.12	Often Favorable
6. Pupils visit their sick classmates/ schoolmates.	3.94	Often
7. Pupils offer their money to help their classmates/schoolmates who are in need.	4.11	Favorable
		Often Favorable Often Favorable

Naturally, most of the children in schools are friendly. This was also evident in Jolo III District where there was favorable school climate for the children to associate themselves, Kelly (1979).

Children, especially during the first day of the classes may look for their partners whom they can lean on Psychologists termed this as "peer".

And this concern for individual pupils is a venae for good, desirable classroom atmosphere where teachers can easily facilitate leaning especially in group work of in socialized recitation method of teaching. This is also a facilitating factor in the implementation of projects in such a way that an individual can lend his personal belongings or project paraphernalia to his classmates.

School Spirit

Table 2c showed the result of the study for the aspect of school spirit. This was found favorable in these selected schools in Jolo District III. That is, the following also occurred "often" the first case "very often" 1) Pupils like their teachers. 2) Pupils like their principal. 3) Pupils talk good about their school. 4) Pupils are happy whenever they do their assignment/homework. 5) Pupils defend their school when it's criticized by others 6) Pupils accept the limitations or weakness of their school 7) Pupils enjoy working with their classmates/schoolmates in making their school clean and beautiful.

Table 2c

Pupils Behavior	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	
School Spirit	4.28	Often	
1. Pupils like their teachers.	4.63	Favorable	
2. Pupils like their principal.	4.48	Very Often	Very
3. Pupils talk good about their school	4.23	Favorable	
4. Pupils are happy whenever they do their assignment/homework.	4.23	Often	
5. Pupils defend their school when it's criticized by others	4.01	Favorable	
6. Pupils accept the limitations or weakness of their school	4.11	Often	
7. Pupils enjoy working with their classmates/schoolmates in making their school clean and beautiful.	4.22	Favorable	
		Often	
		Favorable	
		Often	
		Favorable	
		Often	
		Favorable	

School spirit implies school identity of school synergy. In the school system especially in the elementary level, children treat their teachers as their second parent. Because of this, sometimes the ideas, values and skills as demonstrated by their teachers become the dominant behavior of the children. Educators have substantiated this manifested behavior to the great extent of contact show between the children and the pupils.

Majority of them would imitate the manners of speaking, listening, writing dressing of their teachers As such, they really love their teacher. This was true to the Jolo District III where school spirit was favorable.

Through this, mutual respect would be observed. And, there would be an ease of instruction, legitimacy of orders like observance of monitoring, prompt submission of assignments and others. In short, there would be an orderly, well-managed class.

Emphasis on Social Life

The teacher in selected School of Jolo District III assured that the emphasis on social life was favorable (Table 2d) Each of the following activities were found "often" in the occurrence 1) Pupils join school organizations or clubs 2) Pupils attend programs and other cultural performances 3) Pupils behave properly during programs and other similar activities in school 4) Pupils look clean, neat, and orderly 5) Pupils work and study together with their classmates. 6) Pupils attend get together activities like acquaintance parties.

Pupils Behavior	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Emphasis on Social Life	4.12	Often
1. Pupils join school organizations or clubs	4.36	Favorable
2. Pupils attend programs and other cultural performances	4.19	Often Favorable
3. Pupils behave properly during programs and other similar activities in school	4.16	Often
4. Pupils look clean, neat, and orderly	3.93	Favorable
5. Pupils work and study together with their classmates.	4.01	Often Favorable
6. Pupils attend get together activities like acquaintance parties.	4.08	Often Favorable Often Favorable Often Favorable

Children profit from parallel and partnership activities which become the basis for more involved group activities in later grades. The outcomes of the group work are usually shared informally in the early grades.

More so, special attention needs to be given to the planning, carrying out, and evaluation of group work in each area of curriculum For example, group activities in reading and arithmetic provided in art and social studies.

Teacher Dimension and pupils Behavior

Table 6 includes the correlation matrix showing the various degrees of relationship between the different aspects of organizational climate and those of the pupils' behavior in the district III of Jolo. The values of r in various cells of the table were obtained through Spearman Rho computation.

It was found that the positive teacher dimensions correlate with pupils behavior except the esprit and the school spirit which were not related to each other. That is, spirit and intimacy significantly correlate with each of the four (4) aspects of pupils behavior such as academic competence, concern for individual pupil, school spirit, and emphasis on social life. It was further found, therefore, that the overall positive teacher dimension were correlated with the overall pupils behavior. The existence and degree of such relationship were indicated by asterisks (* and ** indicate significant relationship at the 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance at 2-tailed tests respectively). This means that as these positive teacher dimensions occur very frequent or often, the more favorable are the pupils behavior.

Negative teacher dimensions hindrance and disengagement do not correlate with each of the four (4) aspects of pupil behavior. That is, the strength or the weaknesses of hindrance and disengagement have nothing to do with the possibility of the change in the pupil behavior.

Organizational Climate	Pupil Behavior				
	Academic Competition	Concern for Individual pupil	School Spirit	Emphasis on Social Life	Overall Pupil Behavior
I – Teacher Dimension					
Positive Dimension	.261*	.326**			
A. Esprit (+)	.442**	.288*	.150	.336*	.280*
B. Intimacy (+)			.298*	.365**	.355**
Negative Dimension	.143	.230			
C. Hindrance (-)	-.050	-.031	.063	.160	.131
D. Disengagement (-)			-.194	-.032	-.045
II – Principal Dimension					
Positive Dimension	.379**	.451**			
A. Consideration	.280*	.273*	.392**	.361**	.422**
B. Thrust	.345**	.230	.347**	.269*	.304**
C. Production Emphasis			.331**	.292*	.303**
Negative Dimension	.085	.073			
D. Aloofness (-)			.047	-.017	.017

Principal Dimension and Pupil Behavior

With reference to table 6 above, findings revealed that the positive principal consideration, thrust and production emphasis were correlated significantly (having significant relationship) with each of the four (4) pupil behavior- academic competence, concern for individual pupil, school spirit and emphasis on social life, except the production emphasis with the concern for individual pupil. Consequently, the overall positive principal dimensions significantly correlate with the overall pupil behavior. That is, as those positive aspects of principal dimension occur very frequently or often. The more favorable will be the pupil behavior. Aloofness, which is considered as a negative aspect, does not significantly correlate with each of the four (4) pupil behavior.

Managers believe that they are the most influential people in the organization. Thinkers have unanimous approval on this statement.

It is actually the manager or the principal should initiate in advance over his subordinates. His decisions, performance, evaluation do not only affect the teachers but as well as the pupils.

In a monocratic type of organization like school, policies and order emanate from above. The chain of command flows from the top. Hence, subordinates reliance rest to the top. And, accountability of the top management like the principal is not confined to his teachers but to the pupils alike.

This was proven in this study where there was a correlation of the principal aspect and pupils' behavior.

Conclusions

From the data gathered, the following were inferred:

1. That the organizational climate under teachers dimension is characterized by teachers quarrel and criticized each other is rejected.
2. That the pupils like their teachers is rejected.
3. That there is a relationship between school climate and pupils behavior is accepted.

Recommendations

1. The principals shall come-up with activities and programs that the several membership of the faculty members can socialize themselves to strengthen cohesiveness.
2. They shall also come-up with strategic programs that there may create intimacy between the pupils and the principal.
3. Minority group especially expressing their sentiments, needs, and demand shall be addressed to prevent the occurring of factionalism or strife among themselves.

4. Follow-up study especially on correlating the pupils' behavior and the managerial performance shall be conducted.
5. Additional variables shall be added to the present study for further explorations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Above all, a comprehensive informed consent form explaining the goals, methods, potential risks and benefits, and confidentiality policies was delivered to each participant. Furthermore, all trial data points were carefully anonymised in cases when the respondents' personal information had no bearing on the trial results. Data collection was conducted in a private environment to preserve participant privacy, and the collected data was kept in a secure archive that was only accessible by the researchers. Despite the differences in their thoughts and points of view, all members were respected in the same spirit. Additionally, the researchers made an effort to give the participants a welcoming and secure environment so they could talk openly about their experiences.

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